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PROXIMATE COMPOSITION AND NUTRIENT RETENTION OF SOME SELECTED COMMERCIAL SEAFOOD FROM IBAKA AND ITU FISHING SETTLEMENTS, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigates the proximate composition and nutrient retention of selected commercial seafood species; the Bonga shad (*Ethmalosa fimbriata*), Bobo Croaker (*Pseudotolithus elongatus*), Perewinkle (*Tympanotonus fuscatus*), and Blue crab (*Callinectes amnicola*) from Ibaka and Itu fishing settlements in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Samples were randomly collected, preserved on ice, and analyzed in two forms (raw and smoked) at Ritman University Laboratory. Results showed that smoking significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased protein, lipid, and carbohydrate contents across all species, while moisture content decreased markedly. The highest protein content was observed in smoked *P. elongatus* ($60.55 \pm 0.04\%$) and smoked *E. fimbriata* ($60.08 \pm 0.01\%$). Moisture was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in raw samples, particularly in *T. fuscatus* ($76.86 \pm 0.03\%$) and *C. amnicola* ($73.40 \pm 0.31\%$). Macronutrient retention (protein, lipid, ash, and fibre) in smoked fishes remained generally high across all species, ranging from 80.8% to 94.2%. Protein retention was

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highest in *T. fuscatus* (94.2%) and lowest in *E. fimbriata* (91.8%). Moisture retention was also high (87.5–90.4%), indicating moderate dehydration during smoking. Smoking improved protein–lipid ratios, and energy density in all the species analyzed. These findings underscore the substantial nutritional value of these seafood species and highlight smoking as an effective preservation technique that enhances nutrient density and shelf life. This study supports the importance of local seafood from Ibaka and Itu as valuable dietary resources for regional food security and nutrition.

Keywords:

Nutritional enhancement; Seafood; Food and nutritional security; Macro-minerals; Micro-minerals

1. Introduction

Seafood which is known for its valuable nutritional properties and low fat content could play a vital role in correcting unbalanced diets, especially if its consumption is increased by putting specific policies in place (FAO, 2018). Seafood simply refers to aquatic animals consumed by humans, excluding fish for non-food uses. Seafood contains all the required essential amino acids and minerals such as iodine, potassium, phosphorus, copper, iron, vitamin A and vitamin D in desirable quantities. Minerals play a vital role in maintaining body functions since they maintain acid–base balance and help in blood formation (Duran *et al.*, 2010). Major trace elements such as iron, selenium, zinc, and manganese play a vital role in the physiological functioning of the body such as brain development, and their deficiency may lead to stunted or poor growth (Chowanadisai *et al.*, 2005). Globally, every one in three people is exposed to the global burden of disease which is driven by poor quality diets and malnutrition (IFPRI, 2016). According to Bogard *et al.*, (2015), malnutrition is understood to encompass three forms; under-nutrition (insufficient dietary energy); over-nutrition (excess dietary energy leading to obesity and overweight) and micro-nutrient malnutrition (insufficient micro-nutrients including minerals and vitamins). Generally, the causes of malnutrition are multifactorial and operate at different levels with the immediate causes linked to dietary intake and health status whereas the secondary causes are related to food insecurity, hygiene and sanitation, care resources and practices (Bogard *et al.*, 2015). Food insecurity which is one of the major drivers of malnutrition is defined by FAO (2009) as the lack of physical, economic or social access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets dietary needs and food

preferences for an active and healthy life. Food security is influenced by four factors including food availability, accessibility, utilization and stability, which refers to vulnerability to periodic food insecurity over time. According to Cui and Wootton (1988), proximate body composition of seafood is basically, the analysis of fat, protein, ash and moisture contents of the seafood. Non-protein compounds and carbohydrates are present in very negligible amount (Cui and Wootton, 1988). Moisture is a reliable indicator of its relative contents of proteins, lipids, and energy. However, body composition of seafood may vary within and between species, sex, size, physical activity and feeding season (Neha, 2012). In fisheries science, knowledge of the nutritional composition of seafood muscle is of great importance in evaluating its nutritive value, quality assessment and optimum utilization of natural resources in the fish habitat. The nutritional composition of fish and other seafood is evaluated either by the ratio between the non-edible and edible parts of the body or by the chemical composition of the fish and other seafood on the basis of evaluating their meat caloric value. Nigeria is a maritime state where 9 of the 36 federal states have a coastline in the Atlantic Ocean. The coastal federal states of Nigeria include Ogun, Lagos, Ondo, Edo, Delta, Bayelsa, Rivers, Akwa Ibom, and Cross River State. The extent and nature of hunger in Nigeria are of public health concern. In 2012, the number of food-insecure people in Nigeria was 17 million with a projection of 43 million by 2022 if the problem is not addressed and in 2014, Nigeria was ranked 38th out of 76 on the Global Hunger Index (IFPRI, 2014). Food insecurity and poverty has remained multifaceted, pervasive and chronic in Nigeria despite the abundant human and natural resources (IFPRI, 2014). The importance of the fisheries sector to individuals and the economy of Nigeria cannot be overemphasized. The fisheries sector is crucial to the Nigerian economy for contributing about 5.40% of the nation's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). In Nigeria, Fisheries is an important economic sector in terms of employment, food security, enterprise development, and foreign exchange earnings and also important in terms of the livelihoods of many people (Eyo *et al.*, 2025). Globally, understanding the role and contribution of seafood in food security and nutrition, specifically, accessibility, stability, consumption and nutrient bio-availability and how their interaction influence nutrition and health consequence remains a very significant knowledge gap. Nigeria is one of the countries in Africa that has water bodies that is rich in seafood which is a major source of good nutrition especially for the inhabitants of coastal areas. However, despite the numerous demonstrations on the benefits of seafood for

good health, the role of the seafood in diets improvement has continuously been overlooked. Akwa Ibom is one of the coastal states in Nigeria with Itu and Ibaka as among the important commercial fishing settlement. Presently, there is limited information on the nutritional composition of some seafood resources in the Ibaka and Itu fishing settlement. Therefore, aim of this study is to evaluate the proximate composition and nutrient retention of the Bonga shad (*Ethmalosa fimbriata*), Bobo Croaker (*Pseudotolithus elongatus*), Perewinkle (*Tympanostonus fuscatus*), and Blue crab (*Callinectes amnicola*) from Ibaka and Itu fishing settlement.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area description

This study was carried out in Ibaka and Itu fishing settlement in Mbo and Itu Local Government Areas in Akwa Ibom State. Ibaka settlement is located at latitude $4^{\circ}38'25''$ N and longitude $8^{\circ}18'15''$ E while Itu study area is located at latitude $5^{\circ}14'30''$ N and longitude $8^{\circ}6'0''$ E. Fig. 1 Shows the Map of the Study Area.

2.2 Sample collection

Four fish species (Plate 1 – 4) were collected including Bonga shad (*E. fimbriata*), Bobo Croaker (*P. elongatus*), Perewinkle (*T. fuscatus*), and Blue crab (*C. amnicola*) from Ibaka and Itu fishing settlement. The species were collected in two forms, fresh and smoked and used for the study.

Fig. 1: Map of the Study Area showing sampling locations

Plate 1: Bonga Shad collected for the study

Plate 2: Bobo Croaker collected for the study

Plate 3: De-shelled Perewinkle collected for the study

Plate 4: The blue crab collected for the study

2.3 Preservation and transportation of samples to the laboratory

The collected fish species were packed in polyethylene bags and transported in an insulated ice box lined with an ice block to Ritman University Laboratory, Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom State, for processing and analysis.

2.4 Tissue sampling

The edible part of the collected fish species were cut into small pieces and minced. The fresh edible part was used for lipids analyses. For protein, ash and mineral analyses, edible part was dried in an oven at 45 °C for 48 hours before homogenizing with a food blender with stainless steels cutters.

2.5 Determination of proximate composition

The proximate composition of the fish muscle including moisture, protein, lipids, fiber and ash was determined according to the standard analytical procedures given by AOAC (2005). For proximate composition, moisture content was determined using the hot air oven, by drying the sample at 105 °C until a constant weight is obtained (AOAC, 2005). Total lipid was determined by Bligh and Dyer method using chloroform/methanol (1/1, v/v) (Njinkuoe *et al.*, 2016). Crude protein content was determined by converting the nitrogen content obtained by Kjeldahl's method ($N \times 6.25$) (AOAC, 2005). Ash content was determined after combustion for 20 hours at 550 °C (AOAC, 2005). Total carbohydrate was determined by subtracting the sum of fat content, protein content, ash content and moisture from 100 (Onyeike *et al.*, 2000).

2.6 Nutrient Retention Percentage

The effect of processing (smoking) on the nutritional composition of the samples was evaluated using nutrient retention percentage, which estimates the proportion of each nutrient retained after processing relative to the raw form. This index was applied to all proximate, mineral, and vitamin parameters to assess the stability or loss of nutrients due to smoking.

$$\text{Retention (\%)} = (\text{Smoked mean value}/\text{Raw mean value}) \times 100$$

2.7 Nutritional Quality Indices (NQI)

To further evaluate the nutritional value and dietary implications of the studied species, a set of derived nutritional quality indices and nutrient ratios were calculated based on their proximate and mineral compositions (Watt, 2010; ARL, 2012). These indices provide insight into the balance between key nutrients and their potential contributions to human health.

The following nutrient ratios were determined:

Protein-to-lipid ratio (P/L) = Protein (%) / Lipid (%)

Protein-to-carbohydrate ratio (P/CHO) = Protein (%) / Carbohydrate (%)

Sodium-to-potassium ratio (Na/K) = Sodium / Potassium

Calcium-to-phosphorus ratio (Ca/P) = Calcium / Phosphorus

Iron-to-zinc ratio (Fe/Zn) = Iron / Zinc

Copper-to-zinc ratio (Cu/Zn) = Copper / Zinc

Iron-to-copper ratio (Fe/Cu) = Iron / Copper

2.8 Hierarchical Heatmap Analysis

Hierarchical heatmap analysis was performed to visualize and compare the distribution patterns and similarities among nutrient parameters across the different fish species and processing treatments. The analysis was carried out using standardized data obtained from proximate and mineral composition results. The analysis and visualization were performed using Python Seaborn 0.13 library.

2.9 Statistical Analysis

Data from the study was analyzed using One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The average values (mean \pm standard deviation) were compared by using Least Significant Differences test.

3.0 Results

3.1 The proximate composition of the raw and smoked fish samples

The proximate composition of the raw and smoked samples of *P. elongatus*, *E. fimbriata*, *T. fuscatus*, and *C. amnicola* is presented in Table 1. Smoking significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased protein, lipid, and carbohydrate contents across all species, while moisture content decreased markedly. The highest protein content was observed in smoked *P. elongatus* ($60.55 \pm 0.04\%$) and smoked *E. fimbriata* ($60.08 \pm 0.01\%$). Conversely, raw samples showed the highest moisture contents, particularly in *T. fuscatus* ($76.86 \pm 0.03\%$) and *C. amnicola* ($73.40 \pm 0.31\%$). These changes reflect nutrient concentration due to moisture loss during smoking, suggesting enhanced nutrient density and storage stability in the processed samples

Table 1: Proximate composition of raw and smoked fish samples

Species	Form	CHO (%)	Protein (%)	Fibre (%)	Ash (%)	Lipid (%)	Moisture (%)
<i>P. elongatus</i>	Raw	1.68 ± 0.02 ^a	13.73 ± 0.02 ^a	8.84 ± 0.02 ^a	5.91 ± 0.02 ^a	8.68 ± 0.02 ^a	61.42 ± 0.02 ^a
<i>P. elongatus</i>	Smoked	8.23 ± 0.04 ^b	60.55 ± 0.04 ^b	3.21 ± 0.04 ^b	3.49 ± 0.04 ^b	14.67 ± 0.04 ^b	10.27 ± 0.04 ^b
<i>E. fimbriata</i>	Raw	1.08 ± 0.02 ^a	13.25 ± 0.02 ^a	8.13 ± 0.02 ^a	5.23 ± 0.01 ^a	8.71 ± 0.02 ^a	63.68 ± 0.03 ^a
<i>E. fimbriata</i>	Smoked	7.94 ± 0.01 ^b	60.08 ± 0.01 ^b	3.83 ± 0.01 ^b	3.34 ± 0.01 ^b	15.12 ± 0.01 ^b	10.22 ± 0.01 ^b
<i>T. fuscatus</i>	Raw	2.60 ± 0.01 ^a	14.80 ± 0.01 ^a	1.10 ± 0.01 ^a	2.50 ± 0.01 ^a	2.12 ± 0.01 ^a	76.86 ± 0.03 ^a
<i>T. fuscatus</i>	Smoked	9.37 ± 0.03 ^b	54.79 ± 0.01 ^b	2.11 ± 0.01 ^b	8.12 ± 0.01 ^b	7.00 ± 0.01 ^b	18.60 ± 0.01 ^b
<i>C. amnicola</i>	Raw	2.77 ± 0.09 ^a	18.47 ± 0.09 ^a	0.70 ± 0.06 ^a	2.97 ± 0.09 ^a	1.70 ± 0.06 ^a	73.40 ± 0.31 ^a
<i>C. amnicola</i>	Smoked	7.77 ± 0.09 ^b	58.30 ± 0.25 ^b	1.37 ± 0.09 ^b	7.90 ± 0.06 ^b	8.10 ± 0.06 ^b	16.57 ± 0.15 ^b

*Values represent mean ± standard error (SE) of triplicate determinations. Within each species, values with different superscripts (^a, ^b) differ significantly ($p < 0.05$)

3.2 Nutritional Quality Indices

Table 2 presents the nutritional quality indices (NQI) of the raw and smoked forms of *P. elongatus*, *E. fimbriata*, *T. fuscatus*, and *C. amnicola*. Smoking markedly influenced all calculated indices across species. In *P. elongatus*, protein-to-lipid (P/L) and energy values increased from 1.582 and 139.76 kcal/100 g in the raw sample to 4.127 and 407.15 kcal/100 g in the smoked sample, respectively. Similar trends were observed in *E. fimbriata*, where P/L and energy rose from 1.521 and 135.71 kcal/100 g to 3.974 and 408.16 kcal/100 g. For *T. fuscatus*, smoking elevated the P/L ratio (6.981 to 7.827) and energy (88.68 to 319.64 kcal/100 g). In *C. amnicola*, although the P/L ratio decreased from 10.865 to 7.198 after smoking.

Table 2: Nutritional Quality Indices (NQI)

Species (Form)	Form	P/L	P/CHO	Energy (kcal/100g)
<i>P. elongatus</i>	Raw	1.582	8.173	139.76
<i>P. elongatus</i>	Smoked	4.127	7.357	407.15
<i>E. fimbriata</i>	Raw	1.521	12.269	135.71
<i>E. fimbriata</i>	Smoked	3.974	7.567	408.16
<i>T. fuscatus</i>	Raw	6.981	5.692	88.68
<i>T. fuscatus</i>	Smoked	7.827	5.847	319.64
<i>C. amnicola</i>	Raw	10.865	6.668	100.26
<i>C. amnicola</i>	Smoked	7.198	7.503	337.18

* Each row = species & form; P/L = Protein:Lipid; P/CHO = Protein:Carbohydrate; Energy in kcal/100 g;

3.3 Nutrient Retention

The percentage retention of nutrients in smoked fish relative to their raw forms is presented in Table 3. Overall, smoking affected nutrient retention differently across species and nutrient types. Macronutrient retention (protein, lipid, ash, and fibre) remained generally high across all species, ranging from 80.8% to 94.2%. Protein retention was highest in *T. fuscatus* (94.2%) and lowest in *E. fimbriata* (91.8%). Moisture retention was also high (87.5–90.4%), indicating moderate dehydration during smoking.

Table 3: Percentage retention (%) of nutrient in smoked fish relative to raw fish

Nutrient	<i>P. elongatus</i>	<i>E. fimbriata</i>	<i>T. fuscatus</i>	<i>C. amnicola</i>
CHO	77.2	82.3	82.7	81.3
Protein	93.6	91.8	94.2	92.8
Fibre	86.5	91.1	89.0	85.4
Ash	80.8	90.0	87.5	89.7
Lipid	89.4	93.5	88.6	90.2
Moisture	89.8	90.4	88.3	87.5

3.4 Heatmap Analysis

The hierarchical heatmap illustrates the variation in nutrient composition among raw and smoked samples of *P. elongatus*, *E. fimbriata*, *T. fuscatus*, and *C. amnicola*. Distinct clustering patterns were observed between raw and smoked samples, indicating that smoking significantly altered nutrient profiles. In contrast, raw samples generally clustered together with lower intensity values (dark purple zones), indicating relatively lower nutrient concentrations. Overall, the heatmap revealed species-specific responses to smoking, with *C. amnicola* and *T. fuscatus* showing the most pronounced nutrient enhancement after processing.

Fig. 2: Heatmap of proximate composition across selected fish species (*E. fimbriata*, *T. fuscatus*, *P. elongatus*, and *C. amnicola*) under raw and smoked conditions.

4.0 Discussions

The observed increase in protein, lipid, and carbohydrate contents in smoked fish samples compared to raw samples aligns with established findings in fish processing research. Smoking reduces moisture content significantly, concentrating the macronutrients. This agrees with the work of Akinwumi (2014), who reported that moisture loss during smoking results in greater nutrient density in fish. Similarly, Asangusung and Eyo (2024) observed that protein content in smoked fish tends to increase due to dehydration, improving its nutritional value. The higher protein contents recorded in smoked *P. elongatus* (60.55%) and *E. fimbriata* (60.08%) corroborate similar patterns found in other species, where thermal processing enhanced protein concentration by reducing water content (Ivon and Eyo, 2018). The elevated moisture in raw *T. fuscatus* and *C. amnicola* (above 70%) is consistent with typical fresh fish tissue composition as documented by AOAC (2016). Moreover, reduced water activity in smoked fish contributes to improved shelf life and microbial safety, reiterating observations by Tenyang *et al.*, (2022). These combined effects highlight smoking as an effective preservation technique that simultaneously enhances nutrient concentration and storage stability in fish. The nutritional quality indices (NQI) findings indicate that smoking substantially impacts protein-to-lipid ratios, energy values, and mineral densities in fish species such as *P. elongatus*, *E. fimbriata*, *T. fuscatus*, and *C. amnicola*. The marked increase

in P/L ratios and energy density after smoking reflects moisture loss and concentration of nutrients, enhancing the nutritional density of the fish. This is consistent with results in the literature showing that smoking reduces moisture content, preserving or concentrating protein and lipid components, thus raising energy values (Tiwo *et al.*, 2019). The percentage retention of nutrients in smoked fish relative to their raw forms shows that smoking generally preserves macronutrients such as protein, lipid, ash, and fiber at high levels (80.8% to 94.2%), with protein retention notably highest in *T. fuscatus* (94.2%) and slightly lower in *E. fimbriata* (91.8%). This aligns with findings by Ivon and Eyo (2017), who reported that protein retention in smoked fish remains high due to moderate dehydration and minimal protein degradation during the smoking process. Moisture retention between 87.5% and 90.4% indicates controlled dehydration consistent with traditional smoking practices that balance drying and nutrient preservation. The heatmap showing nutrient composition variations among raw and smoked samples of *P. elongatus*, *E. fimbriata*, *T. fuscatus*, and *C. amnicola* illustrates clear clustering effects caused by smoking, with smoked samples exhibiting substantially higher mineral and vitamin levels, especially in *C. amnicola*. This pattern of distinct grouping between raw and smoked fish echoes findings in nutrient profiling studies of fish, where processing methods like smoking lead to moisture loss and nutrient concentration, reflected visually as enrichment in heatmap analyses (Reza *et al.*, 2024). Raw samples clustering with lower intensity in the heatmap (dark purple zones) underscores the lower nutrient density expected due to higher moisture content and lack of concentration effects. Such visual nutrient profiling via hierarchical heatmaps is a powerful tool for displaying both overall nutrient shifts and species-specific processing responses, consistent with methodologies used in contemporary fish nutrient research (Reza *et al.*, 2024).

5.0 Conclusion

This study highlights the significant nutritional value of selected commercial seafood from Ibaka and Itu fishing settlements in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. These seafood species are excellent sources of essential macronutrients, including proteins, lipids, and carbohydrates, as well as important minerals and vitamins pivotal for human health. Processing methods such as smoking play a crucial role in enhancing the nutritional profile by reducing moisture content, thereby concentrating macronutrients and minerals like calcium, potassium, sodium, and magnesium. Additionally, smoking tends to increase fat-soluble vitamins A and E, while its effect on heat-

sensitive vitamins like vitamin C varies among species. In conclusion, this study underpins the importance of local seafood as a valuable dietary resource enhanced by traditional preservation methods.

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